

Oral Hygiene Status and Dental Caries Experience in Patients with Dental Fluorosis Visiting A Private Dental Institution in Chennai

Research Article

Nivetha G¹, Sri Sakthi D^{2*}, Arvind S³

¹ Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, India.

² Reader, Department of Public Health Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, 600077, India.

³ Reader, Department of Orthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, 600077, India.

Abstract

Dental fluorosis exhibits as enamel mottling, surface irregularities, leading to plaque accumulation and thereby leading to dental caries and periodontal diseases. The aim of the study was find out the association of oral hygiene status and dental caries in patients with dental fluorosis visiting Saveetha Dental College. A retrospective study was carried out in Saveetha Dental College between June 2019-March 2020. The study population consisted of young adults who reported with dental fluorosis. The data was collected from patients records analysed from the data of 86000 patients between June 2019-March 2020 and entered in Excel sheets. The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS software. A chi square test was done and a p value of < 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant. The independent variables present in this study were age and gender. The dependent variables were fluorosis, DMFT and OHI scores. The results showed that 53% of fluorosis patients had less than score of dental caries status and 56% of fluorosis had fair oral hygiene status. The study concludes that a lesser degree of dental caries and fair oral hygiene status were found in out patients with dental fluorosis.

Keywords: Fluorosis; Oral Health; Young Adults.

Introduction

Oral health is recognised and accepted as equally important when compared to general health. Oral health can be defined as standard health of the oral and related tissues which enables individuals to eat, speak and socialize without active-disease, discomfort which contribute to general health [1]. Oral disease can be considered as a public health problem due to their higher prevalence and social impact [2]. Poor oral health affects the quality of life in children, adults and old people. In adults, routine daily activities may be disrespected and lead to economic loss [3]. Poor oral hygiene and nutritional practices disturb the ecological homeostasis in plaque thereby causing an inexorable shift in plaque ecology towards highly cariogenic microorganisms [4].

Dental caries are multifactorial, primarily depending on host,

agent and environmental factors. It is formed by the interaction between acid producing bacteria and fermentable carbohydrate which leads to a break in the balance between demineralization and remineralization [5]. *Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus* are the primary causative microorganisms for the development of dental caries [6]. It is the most common chronic disease that interferes with normal nutrition intake, speech, and daily routine activities. Dental caries are the major oral health problems and indicators of oral health problems all over the world [7]. The prevalence of dental caries has high graded society and wide geographic spread [8]. Fluoride is an essential component for normal mineralization of bones and dental enamel [9]. The main source of fluoride for the human body is usually in drinking water that covers about 75-90% of daily intake [10]. The higher concentrations of fluoride causes serious health problems namely dental fluorosis, skeletal fluorosis and non-skeletal fluo-

*Corresponding Author:

Sri Sakthi,
Reader, Department of Public Health Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, 600077, India.
Tel: 8122399966
E-mail: srisakthi@saveetha.com

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rosis. Dental fluorosis is considered the earliest sign of fluoride intoxication. Fluorosis may have direct as well as indirect effect on oral hygiene status. It causes failure of cemental resorption leading to hypercementosis and osteonecrosis [11]. Indirectly, it causes plaque associated periodontal disease [12].

Fluorides is the protective agent for dental caries [13]. The use of fluorides for prevention of dental caries has been proven to be a safe and effective public health strategy to reduce the burden of dental disease of the population in industrialized and developing countries. Adequate program monitoring and quality control maintenance can minimize occurrence of enamel mottling in communities using fluorides for dental caries prevention [14]. Previously our team has conducted numerous cross sectional studies [7, 15, 16], clinical trials [4, 6, 17-20], *in-vitro* studies [9, 21, 24] and review (25 over the past 5 years. Now we are focussing on epidemiological surveys. The present aimed to find out the degree of dental caries and oral hygiene status in fluorosis patients among young adults who visiting Saveetha Dental College.

Materials and Methods

Study design

Retrospective study.

Study population

A retrospective study was carried out among young adults reporting to Saveetha Dental College and Hospital. The study was conducted between June 2019-March 2020. The study population consisted of young adults .i.e 18-35 years who were reported with dental fluorosis.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee and Scientific Review Board (SRB) of Saveetha Dental College. SDC/SIHEC/2020/DIASDATA/0619-0320.

Data collection

The data were collected by analyzing the records of 86000 patients between June 2019-March 2020. The data comprised 100 patients who were reported with dental fluorosis. The data includes patient's details, OHI score, DMFT score and fluorosis

score. The dental fluorosis were assessed by Dean's Fluorosis Index and categorized as very mild, mild and questionable. The oral hygiene status were assessed by Oral Hygiene Simplified Index and categorized as good, fair and poor. The dental caries status were assessed by DMFT (Decayed-Missing-Filled-Teeth index) and categorized as score of less than 5, 5-10 and greater than 10.

Data analysis

The collected data were entered in Excel sheet and subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS software. Chi square test were done between DMFT and fluorosis score, OHI and fluorosis and OHI and DMFT. The independent variables were age and gender while dependent variables were OHI, DMFT and fluorosis. The level of significance is $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Dental fluorosis is recognised as an oral health disease of public health. It results in poor esthetic appearance which may have a psychological bearing and leading to low confidence level [26]. Adulthood is the stage where the individuals lay the foundation for oral health, environmental factors, parental care, socioeconomic status are the elements which shapes the individuals attitude towards oral hygiene and treatment needs.

Our aim in this study was to find out the association of oral hygiene status, dental caries in fluorosis patients visiting Saveetha Dental College. Totally, 100 fluorosis patients were included in this study. About 41% were 18-25 age group, 47% were 26-32 age group and 12% were 32+ age group (chart 1). Out of 100 fluorosis patients, 77% were Male and 23% were females (chart 2).

Majority of patients with very mild fluorosis had fair oral hygiene status and < 5 DMFT score whereas patients with mild fluorosis had fair oral hygiene status and were in 5-10 DMFT score category. Patients with questionable fluorosis had fair oral hygiene status and < 5 DMFT score status. About 56% fluorosis patients had scores of > 5 DMFT score which was found to be statistically not significant (graph 1). Previous studies conducted by Sudhakar et al, Koteha et al, Tsutusi et al and Mascarenhas et al [27-30] reported with lesser degree of dental caries status in dental fluorosis patients which is similar to our present study. 53% of dental fluorosis patients had fair oral hygiene status. Association between OHI(s) and dental fluorosis was found to be statistically not significant (graph 4). The study conducted by Vora k et al,

Chart 1. Depicts the distribution of study population based on age. It shows that most number of patients with dental fluorosis were seen in 26-32 years age group [47.00%] followed by 18-25 years age group [41.00%] and least was among 33+ years age group [12.00%].

Shetty et al., and Reddy et al., [31-33] concluded that poor oral hygiene status was seen in dental fluorosis patients which was dissimilar to our present study. More number of patients with fair oral hygiene status had <5 DMFT score. A chi square analysis was done to check the association between DMFT score and Oral hygiene status of study population, even though a difference was observed based on the level of oral hygiene, it was not found to be statistically significant (graph 5).

Limitation

The main of this study is limited sample size and confined to a single source for data. Further descriptive studies on a larger scale can help us to give comprehensive data for arriving at a conclusion and to plan health oral health programs for the population

studied.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of the current study, it can be concluded that low to moderate level of caries risk was found in patients with dental fluorosis and cumulatively the oral hygiene status of the patients was found to be fair; indicating the need to educate the patients on proper brushing methods and oral hygiene practice, thereby reducing the dental caries risk also.

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Chart 2. Depicts the distribution of study population based on gender. It shows that more number of male patients [77.00%] reported with dental fluorosis when compared to female patients [23.00%].

Graph 1. This graph represents the association between DMFT score and dental fluorosis in young adult patients. X axis represents DMFT score of patients and Y axis represents number of patients with different degrees of dental fluorosis. It was seen that majority of patients with very mild fluorosis (blue) had DMFT score less than 5. Chi square test was done (p-value=0.603), and it was not significant. Hence proving that there is no significant association between dental caries experience and different degree of fluorosis.

Graph 2. This graph represents the association between OHI(s) and dental fluorosis of young adults. X axis represents OHI score of patients and Y axis represents number of patients with degree of dental fluorosis. It was seen that the majority of patients with fair oral hygiene status had very mild dental fluorosis (green). Chi square test was done (p-value=0.209), and it was not significant. proving that there is no significant association between Oral hygiene status of patients and patients with different degrees of dental fluorosis.

Graph 3. This graph represents the association between OHI(s) and DMFT scores of young adults. X axis represents DMFT score of patients and Y axis represents number of patients based on their oral hygiene status. Even though, majority of the patients with good (blue) and Fair (red) oral hygiene were in <5 and 5-10 DMFT score category, A chi square test done (p-value=0.884), revealed no statistically significant association between the two variables in the study population.

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